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ERC Data Management Plan

**Coevolution of Life and Planet: role of trace metal
availability in the evolution of biogeochemically
relevant redox metalloenzymes**

CoEvolve

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DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN SUMMARY

This document represents the Data Management Plan (DMP) developed for ERC funded project CoEvolve, and aims to describe all the data that will be collected and generated during the project, as well as explain how the data will be made public, shared for re-use and how it will be stored. This DMP follows the ERC data management template guidelines. The CoEvolve project is committed to follow the “FAIR” data principles, and this represents a living document outlining how the data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable during and beyond the duration of the project. The CoEvolve DMP will be updated regularly to reflect any change in the type, volume or management of the data produced.

PROJECT SUMMARY

Earth’s geosphere and biosphere have coevolved over time, influencing each other’s stability and keeping our planet habitable over the last 4 billion years. Biogeochemical cycles are crucial in this mechanism, connecting long-term geological cycles and the much faster evolution of the Earth’s outer envelopes. A small set of microbial-encoded proteins containing a redox-sensitive transition metal as their core catalytic center carry out the majority of the key biogeochemical reactions. Metals such as Fe, Co, Ni, Zn, Mo, W, V, and Cu are used in these proteins to access diverse redox couples as a function of what the planet has provided to biology over time. Despite the importance of this process, the relationship between metal availability and metabolism evolution and diversity has not been investigated in detail. COEVOLVE will elucidate the impact of transition metal availability on microbial functional diversity in deep time, combining fieldwork, laboratory experiments, and computational approaches. COEVOLVE will: 1) investigate the relationship between the availability of trace metals and microbial functional diversity in extant ecosystems and organisms; 2) link metabolic diversity and metal availability to different geological, geochemical, and mineralogical conditions; 3) link metabolic diversity and dependence on metal availability to the emergence and evolution of different metabolisms; and 4) determine the timing of major steps in metabolic evolution and link them to geochemical proxies of planetary surface redox change. Understanding the role of trace metal environmental distribution and availability in influencing microbial functional diversity might hold the key to understanding the co-evolution of life and our planet, unlocking a number of important discoveries at the core of diverse fields such as earth sciences, astrobiology, microbial ecology, and biotechnology.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

CoEvolve aims to produce a large amount of raw and derived data that consists of microbiological, genomic, geochemical and mineralogical data from both expeditions and laboratory experiments.

Several terabytes of sequencing data are expected, with additional data generated for the geochemistry and mineralogy of each sampling site planned in the project. Additionally, large databases of interdisciplinary data will be generated. For example, protocols and standard operating practices for quality assessment, -omics/geochemistry data integration and subsequent statistical and data analysis will be made publicly available. Additionally, new data analysis tools and visualization techniques will be developed, and ultimately shared, to address specific challenges arising from integrating the data obtained.

For a complex and ambitious project like the ERC CoEvolve it is difficult to predict all the kinds of data that will be produced in the upcoming years. The type of data we expect to produce are classified and outlined below. However, the list will be updated as the project progresses in case we will collect or produce types of data that do not fit into the categories already identified or that require new standards. Remains clear that any data produced by the ERC CoEvolve project will always comply with the FAIR principles.

Expected data will be divided in the following categories:

- **Metadata:** includes the unique and persistent identifiers of each sample, geographic coordinates, sampling methods and other information that is going to increase the interoperability of the datasets;
- **Geoscience data:** include all the geology, mineralogy and geochemistry data (for example stable isotopes measurements, trace elements composition, major ions, etc...);
- **Bioscience data:** include data collected via laboratory experiments or biological measurements that cannot be classified as nucleic acid sequences or protein mass spectra (for example cell count, flow cytometry, growth rates, etc...);
- **Sequencing data:** include all the DNA sequences obtained from sequencing approaches;
- **Protein data:** include all the protein sequences obtained from proteomic approaches;
- **Other** type of data

FAIR DATA

Making data findable

The data generated within the ERC CoEvolve project will be deposited in public storage data repositories that can attribute persistent unique identifiers (DOI), and structured to be easily combinable with other datasets. Table 1 reports the chosen repositories for data sets publication and preservation and the data volume expected, however we maintain the flexibility to add or change the chosen repositories if at the time of data release we will identify new more appropriate repositories that comply with FAIR principles. We intend to deposit all the sequencing data in the ENA repository under a unique Umbrella Study for the CoEvolve project, which provides a hierarchical grouping that will allow us to deposit each sampling campaign separately but still keep it related to the others.

Table 1. Summary of data repositories and data volume expected

Type of data	Data Format	Volume expected	Repository	Repository links
Metadata	ISA-tab	~200 MB	GitHub-Zenodo ISA-tool	https://github.com/ https://zenodo.org/ https://isa-tools.org/
Geoscience data	csv	~200 MB	EarthChem Pangea Github-Zenodo	https://www.earthchem.org/ https://www.pangaea.de/ https://github.com/
Bioscience data	csv	~200 MB	Pangea Dryad GitHub-Zenodo	https://www.pangaea.de/ https://datadryad.org/stash https://github.com/ https://zenodo.org/
Sequencing data	Fastq	~5 TB	ENA	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home
Protein data	mzTab	~1 TB	ProteomExchange	http://www.proteomexchange.org/
Other type of data			GitHub-Zenodo	https://github.com/ https://zenodo.org/

Making data openly accessible

Besides restrictions imposed by the advancement of the project, the data will be released at the time of publication or within two years of their production. Research data will be converted to well-known open formats in order to facilitate accessibility, shareability and reusability. To increase the accessibility and reproducibility of data, the Giovannelli Lab associates to each publication a unique DOI number generated with Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) containing all the data merged and deposited in a GitHub (<https://github.com/>) repository with source codes and protocol specifications to reproduce

the analyses. The ERC CoEvolve project will follow the same practice, releasing a unique version of the data, protocols and code used for each publication.

Making data interoperable

All ERC CoEvolve data will be connected through metadata, so that data streams coming from different sources are connected by unique persistent identifiers that allow to superimpose variables from different datasets. Publications also increase the interoperability of data, acting as a meeting point between data from different sources, as well as the use of internationally accepted data exchange formats. To increase the interoperability of the data, all CoEvolve data will be integrated and made available in a new online relational database developed for the project (<https://www.coevolvedb.org/>), which will allow to integrate the different layers containing data from different sources linking all the public repositories used for specific data.

Increase data re-use

Choosing trusted and accessible public repositories, using a unique DOI linking all the data, source codes and protocol used in each published study and deposited in a GitHub repository to increase reproducibility, adding information on how data can be used and reused and how to cite the data, and releasing data-focused publications (such as in Scientific Data or similar journals) will help to increase data discoverability and citability. Once released data will be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible. Normally a CC-BY 4.0 type of license will be used (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), unless a more appropriate license is available for the specific data type. Data will be made public as soon as possible, while still allowing for time to publish by the project members. To ensure speed of dissemination, all obtained results will be published as preprint in public preprint servers (BioArXiv <https://www.biorxiv.org/>, EarthArXiv <https://eartharxiv.org/>, PeerJ Preprints <https://peerj.com/preprints/>, etc...). Data will be made available at time of preprint submission or two years after being produced, whichever comes first. The CoEvolve project does not foresee the production of sensitive data, however if the need for more restriction arises the DMP will be updated accordingly.

Allocation of resources and data security

The ERC CoEvolve project will use 3,000-5,000 € per year to build and maintain the CoEvolve Project Database (<https://www.coevolvedb.org/>). The responsible for the implementation of this data management plan is the CoEvolve PI, Donato Giovannelli. In addition, a member of the team has been identified as Deputy Data Manager for the project and will be responsible for bringing to action all aspects of the DMP. In addition, all the researchers involved in the project will share the responsibility toward FAIR principles implementation.